

AUTOMATIC CAMERA ORIENTATION AND STRUCTURE RECOVERY WITH SAMANTHA

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ABSTRACT:

SAMANTHA is a software capable of computing camera orientation and structure recovery from a sparse block of casual images without human intervention. It can process both calibrated images or uncalibrated, in which case an autocalibration routine is run. Pictures are organized into a hierarchical tree which has single images as leaves and partial reconstructions as internal nodes. The method proceeds bottom up until it reaches the root node, corresponding to the final result. This framework is one order of magnitude faster than sequential approaches, inherently parallel, less sensitive to the error accumulation causing drift. We have verified the quality of our reconstructions both qualitatively producing compelling point clouds and quantitatively, comparing them with laser scans serving as ground truth.

1 INTRODUCTION

Three dimensional (3D) content is pervasive in most forms of digital media, feeding the need for ubiquitous, effortless acquisition of 3D models. In this article we describe SAMANTHA, an automatic, robust software that can compute camera orientation and scene structure from a sparse block of casual (unconstrained) digital images. Picture datasets are easy to capture, process and update. They have better resolution, contrast, definition of the video that can be produced with equally priced equipment. Pictures have also inferior requirements for storage and globally lower costs for production, maintenance and processing. Images are therefore the preferred way for ubiquitous, low cost acquisition of quality 3D data.

In Computer Vision the problem of recovering camera (external) orientation and scene 3D structure from images is known as *Structure and Motion*. If the internal orientation is unknown it must be computed as well and the problem becomes *uncalibrated*.

Relevant literature comprises several Structure and Motion (SaM) pipelines that process images in batch and handle the reconstruction process making no assumptions on the imaged scene and on the acquisition rig (Brown and Lowe, 2005, Kamberov et al., 2006, Snavely et al., 2006, Vergauwen and Gool, 2006, Irschara et al., 2007).

The main issue to be solved in this context is the scalability of the SaM pipeline. This prompted a quest for efficiency that has explored several different solutions: the most successful have been those aimed at reducing the impact of the bundle adjustment phase, which – with feature extraction – dominates the computational complexity.

A class of solutions that have been proposed are the so-called *partitioning methods* (Fitzgibbon and Zisserman, 1998). They reduce the reconstruction problem into smaller and better conditioned subproblems which can be effectively optimized. The subproblems can be selected analytically as in (Steedly et al., 2003), where spectral partitioning has been applied to SaM, or they can emerge from the underlying 3D structure of the problem, as described in (Ni et al., 2007). The computational gain of

such methods is obtained by limiting the combinatorial explosion of the algorithm complexity as the number of images and feature points increases.

A second strategy is to select a subset of the input images and feature points that subsumes the entire solution. Hierarchical subsampling was pioneered by (Fitzgibbon and Zisserman, 1998), using a balanced tree of trifocal tensors over a video sequence. The approach was subsequently refined by (Nistér, 2000), adding heuristics for redundant frames suppression and tensor triplet selection. In (Shum et al., 1999) the sequence is divided into segments, which are resolved locally. They are subsequently merged hierarchically, eventually using a representative subset of the segment frames. A similar approach is followed in (Gibson et al., 2002), focusing on obtaining a well behaved segment subdivision and on the robustness of the following merging step. The advantage of these methods over their sequential counterparts lays in the fact that they improve error distribution on the entire dataset and bridge over degenerate configurations. Anyhow, they work for video sequences, so they cannot be applied to unordered, sparse images.

A recent paper (Snavely et al., 2006) that works with sparse datasets describes a way to select a subset of images whose reconstruction provably approximates the one obtained using the entire set. This considerably lowers the computational requirements by controllably removing redundancy from the dataset. Even in this case, however, the images selected are processed incrementally. Moreover, this method does not avoid computing the epipolar geometry between *all* pairs of images.

A third solution is covered in literature, orthogonal to the aforementioned approaches. In (Agarwal et al., 2009), the computational complexity of the reconstruction is tackled by throwing additional computational power to the problem. Within such framework, the former algorithmical challenges are substituted by load balancing and subdivision of reconstruction tasks. Such direction of research strongly suggest that the current monolithic pipelines should be modified to accommodate ways to parallelize and optimally split the workflow of reconstruction tasks.

Our proposal is a hierarchical and parallelizable scheme for SaM. The images are organized into a hierarchical cluster tree, the re-

construction proceeding from leaves to the root. Partial reconstructions correspond to internal nodes, whereas images are stored in the leaves (see Fig. 1). This scheme provably cuts the computational complexity by one order of magnitude (provided that the dendrogram is well balanced) and achieves scalability by partitioning the problem into smaller instances and combining them hierarchically in a inherently parallelizable way. It is also less sensible to typical problems of sequential approaches, namely sensitivity to initialization (Thormählen et al., 2004) and drift (Cornelis et al., 2008). This approach has some analogy with (Schaffalitzky and Zisserman, 2002), where a spanning tree is built to establish in which order the images must be processed. After that, however, the images are processed in a standard incremental way.

Figure 1: An example of dendrogram for a 6 views set.

Most existing pipelines either assumes known internal parameters (Brown and Lowe, 2005, Irschara et al., 2007), or constant internal parameters (Vergauwen and Gool, 2006, Kamberov et al., 2006), or relies on EXIF data plus external informations (camera CCD dimensions) (Snively et al., 2006). Another unique feature of SAMANTHA is the capability of dealing with uncalibrated images with varying internal parameters and no ancillary information, as it leverages on a novel auto-calibration procedure robust enough to be applied in a real context.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. The next section outlines the matching stage, then Sec. 3 describes the way the hierarchical cluster tree is built. Section 4 presents the hierarchical approach to structure and motion recovery, whereas the autocalibration strategy is explained in Sec. 5. We will then describe the online image orientation stage in Sec. 6. Experimental detailed in Sec. 7, and finally conclusions are drawn in Sec. 8.

2 KEYPOINT MATCHING

In this section we describe the stage of SAMANTHA that is devoted to the automatic extraction and matching of keypoints among all the n available images. Its output is to be fed into the geometric stage, that will perform the actual reconstruction.

The objective is to identify in a computationally efficient way images that potentially share a good number of keypoints, instead of trying to match keypoints between every image pair (they are $O(n^2)$). We follow the approach of (Brown and Lowe, 2003). SIFT (Lowe, 2004) keypoints are extracted in all n images. In this culling phase we consider only a constant number of descriptors in each image (300 in our experiments, where a typical image contains thousands of SIFT keypoints). Then, each keypoint description is matched to its ℓ nearest neighbors in feature space (we use $\ell = 8$). This can be done in $O(n \log n)$ time by using a k-d tree to find approximate nearest neighbors (we used the ANN library (Mount and Arya, 1996)). A 2D histogram is then built that registers in each bin the number of matches between the corresponding views. Every image will be matched only to the m images that have the greatest number of keypoints matches with

it (we use $m = 8$). Hence, the number of images to match is $O(n)$, being m constant.

Matching follows a nearest neighbor approach (Lowe, 2004), with rejection of those keypoints for which the ratio of the nearest neighbor distance to the second nearest neighbor distance is greater than a threshold (set to 1.5 in our experiments).

Homographies and fundamental matrices between pairs of matching images are then computed using MSAC (Torr and Zisserman, 2000). Let e_i be the residuals after MSAC, the final set of inliers are those points such that

$$|e_i - \text{med}_j e_j| < 3.5\sigma^*, \quad (1)$$

where σ^* is a robust estimator of the scale of the noise:

$$\sigma^* = 1.4826 \text{med}_i |e_i - \text{med}_j e_j|. \quad (2)$$

This outlier rejection rule is called X84 in (Hampel et al., 1986).

The model parameters are eventually re-estimated on this set of inliers via least-squares minimization of the (first-order approximation of the) geometric error (Luong and Faugeras, 1996, Chum et al., 2005).

The more likely model (homography or fundamental matrix) is selected according to the Geometric Robust Information Criterion (GRIC) (Torr, 1997). Finally, if the number of remaining matches between two images is less than a threshold (computed basing on a statistical test as in (Brown and Lowe, 2003)) then they are discarded.

Keypoints matching in multiple images are connected into *tracks*, rejecting as inconsistent those tracks in which more than one keypoint converges (Snively et al., 2006) and those shorter than three frames.

3 VIEWS CLUSTERING

The second stage of SAMANTHA consists in organizing the available views into a hierarchical cluster structure that will guide the reconstruction process.

Algorithms for image views clustering have been proposed in literature in the context of reconstruction (Schaffalitzky and Zisserman, 2002), panoramas (Brown and Lowe, 2003), image mining (Quack et al., 2008) and scene summarization (Simon et al., 2007). The distance being used and the clustering algorithm are application-specific.

The method starts from an affinity matrix among views, computed using the following measure, that takes into account the number of common keypoints and how well they are spread over the images:

$$a_{i,j} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{|S_i \cap S_j|}{|S_i \cup S_j|} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{CH(S_i) + CH(S_j)}{A_i + A_j} \quad (3)$$

where S_i and S_j are the set of matching keypoints in image I_i and I_j respectively, $CH(\cdot)$ is the area of the convex hull of a set of points and A_i (A_j) is the total area of the image. Figure 2 shows an example of the neighborhood defined by this affinity.

Views are grouped together by agglomerative clustering, which produces a hierarchical, binary cluster tree, called *dendrogram*. The general agglomerative clustering algorithm proceeds in a bottom-up manner: starting from all singletons, each sweep of the algorithm merges the two clusters with the smallest distance. The

Figure 2: An example of one image (top left) from “Piazza Bra” and its five closest neighbors according to the affinity defined in Eq. 3.

way the distance between clusters is computed produces different flavors of the algorithm, namely the simple linkage, complete linkage and average linkage (Duda and Hart, 1973). We selected the *simple linkage* rule: the distance between two clusters is determined by the distance of the two closest objects (nearest neighbors) in the different clusters.

Simple linkage clustering is appropriate to our case because: i) the clustering problem *per se* is fairly simple, ii) nearest neighbors information is readily available with ANN and iii) it produces “elongated” or “stringy” clusters which fits very well with the typical spatial arrangement of images sweeping a certain area or a building.

This procedure allows to decrease the computational complexity with respect to a sequential SaM pipeline, from $O(n^5)$ to $O(n^4)$ in the best case (see (Gherardi et al., 2010) for a complete proof), i.e. when the tree is well balanced (n is the number of views). If the tree is unbalanced this computational gain vanishes. It is therefore crucial to enforce the balancing of the tree and this is the goal of the technique that we shall describe in this section.

In order to produce better balanced trees and approximate best-case complexity, we modify the agglomerative clustering strategy as follows: starting from all singletons, each sweep of the algorithm merges the pair with the smallest cardinality among the ℓ closest pair of clusters. The distance is computed according to the simple linkage rule. The cardinality of a pair is the sum of the cardinality of the two clusters.

In this way we are softening the “closest first” agglomerative criterion by introducing a competing “smallest first” principle that tends to produce better balanced dendrograms. The amount of balancing is regulated by the parameter ℓ : when $\ell = 1$ this is the standard agglomerative clustering with no balancing; when $\ell \geq n/2$ (n is the number of views) a perfect balanced tree is obtained, but the clustering is poor, since distance is largely disregarded. We found in our experiments (see Sec. 7) that a good compromise is $\ell = 5$. An example is shown in 3. The height of the tree is reduced from 14 to 9 and more initial pairs are present in the dendrogram on the right. Computational complexity decrease accordingly.

Extra care must be taken when building clusters of cardinality two. These are pair of images from which the reconstruction will start, hence pairs related by homographies should be avoided. This is tantamount to say that the fundamental model must explain the data far better than an homography, and this can be implemented by considering the GRIC, as in (Pollefeys et al., 2002). We therefore modify the linkage strategy so that two views i and view j are allowed to merge in a cluster only if:

$$\text{gric}(F_{i,j}) < \alpha \text{gric}(H_{i,j}) \quad \text{with } \alpha \geq 1, \quad (4)$$

where $\text{gric}(F_{i,j})$ and $\text{gric}(H_{i,j})$ are the GRIC scores obtained by the fundamental matrix and the homography matrix respectively (we used $\alpha = 1.2$). If the test fail, consider the second closest elements and repeat.

4 HIERARCHICAL STRUCTURE AND MOTION

The dendrogram produced by the clustering stage imposes a hierarchical organization of the views that will be followed by SAMANTHA. At every node in the dendrogram an action must be taken, that augment the reconstruction (cameras + 3D points): a two views reconstruction is *per/for/med* when a cluster is first created, then there can be the addition of a single view to an existing cluster or the merging of two clusters. The first two are the typical operations of a sequential pipeline, whereas the latter is unique to the hierarchical pipeline.

Each node is upgraded, as soon as possible, possible, to a Euclidean frame. If cameras are calibrated (internal orientation is known) then the Euclidean frame is available from start. If not, autocalibration is run on nodes with a minimum of m views, where m depends on the conditions (for example, autocalibration with known skew and aspect ratio requires a minimum of 4 views to obtain a unambiguous solution).

4.1 Two-views reconstruction.

The reconstruction from two views proceeds from the fundamental matrix. It is well known that the following two camera matrices:

$$P_1 = [T \mid \mathbf{0}] \quad \text{and} \quad P_2 = [[\mathbf{e}_2] \times F \mid \mathbf{e}_2], \quad (5)$$

yield the fundamental matrix F , as can be easily verified.

This canonical pair is related to the correct one (up to a similarity) by a projectivity H of 3D space. Section 5 will describe how to guess a matrix H that provides a well conditioned starting point for the subsequent autocalibration step.

Given the upgraded versions of the perspective projection matrices $P_1 H$ and $P_2 H$, the position in space of the 3D points is then obtained by triangulation (Sec. 4.1.1) and bundle adjustment is run to improve the reconstruction.

4.1.1 Triangulation. Triangulation (or intersection) is performed by the iterated linear LS method (Hartley and Sturm, 1997). Points are pruned by analyzing the condition number of the linear system and the reprojection error. The first test discards ill-conditioned 3D points, using a threshold on the condition number of the linear system (10^4 , in our experiments). The second test applies the so-called X84 rule (Hampel et al., 1986), that establishes that, if e_i are the residuals, the inliers are those points such that

$$|e_i - \text{med}_j e_j| < 5.2 \text{med}_i |e_i - \text{med}_j e_j|. \quad (6)$$

4.2 One-view addition.

The reconstructed 3D points that are visible in the view to be added provides a set of 3D-2D correspondences, that are exploited to glue the view to the cluster. This can be done by resection with DLT (Hartley and Zisserman, 2003), using MSAC (Torr and Zisserman, 2000) to cope with outliers. The view that has been glued might have brought in some new tracks, that are triangulated as described before (Sec. 4.1.1). Finally, bundle adjustment is run on the current reconstruction.

Figure 3: Two dendrograms produced on a 52-views set. The left one was produced using the standard simple linkage rule, the right using the modified rule, with $\ell = 5$.

4.3 Clusters merging.

When two clusters merge the respective reconstructions live in two different reference systems, that are related by a projectivity of the space (which is a similarity when both are properly calibrated). The points that they have in common are the tie points that serve to the purpose of computing the unknown transformation, using MSAC to discard wrong matches. An homography of the projective space is sought that brings the second onto the first, thereby obtaining the correct basis for the second. Once the cameras are registered, the common 3D points are re-computed by triangulation (Sec. 4.1.1), and the tracks obtained after the merging as well. The new reconstruction is eventually refined with bundle adjustment.

5 AUTO-CALIBRATION

SAMANTHA strive to enforce Euclidean structure inside each node of the tree. This is of course not always possible, in particular (in the uncalibrated case) for nodes at the lowest level of the hierarchy, composed by a low number of views. For these nodes, a quasi-Euclidean upgrade will suffice until the minimum number of views or a unambiguous configuration is reached.

Our approach (Gherardi and Fusiello, 2010) is based on a novel method for the estimation of the plane at infinity given an estimate for the internal parameters of at least two cameras. Equipped with such procedure, we can then explore exhaustively the space of valid calibration parameters (which is naturally bounded because of the finiteness of acquisition devices) while looking for the best rectifying homography.

The canonical pair of camera matrices

$$P_1 = [I | \mathbf{0}] \quad \text{and} \quad P_2 = [Q_2 | \mathbf{e}_2], \quad (7)$$

is related to the Euclidean one by a projectivity H of 3D space that has the following structure:

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{v}^\top & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Given reasonable assumptions on internal parameters of the cameras K_1 and K_2 , the upgraded, metric versions of the perspective projection matrices are equal to:

$$P_1^E = [K_1 | \mathbf{0}] \simeq P_1 H \quad (9)$$

$$P_2^E = K_2 [R_2 | \mathbf{t}_2] \simeq P_2 H = [Q_2 K_1 + \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{v}^\top | \mathbf{e}_2] \quad (10)$$

The rotation R_2 can therefore be equated to the following:

$$R_2 \simeq K_2^{-1} (Q_2 K_1 + \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{v}^\top) = K_2^{-1} Q_2 K_1 + \mathbf{t}_2 \mathbf{v}^\top \quad (11)$$

in which it is expressed as the sum of a 3 by 3 matrix and a rank 1 term. Let R^* be the rotation such that: $R^* \mathbf{t}_2 = [||\mathbf{t}_2|| \ 0 \ 0]^\top$. Left multiplying it to Eq. 11 yields:

$$R^* R_2 \simeq R^* \overbrace{K_2^{-1} Q_2 K_1}^W + [||\mathbf{t}_2|| \ 0 \ 0]^\top \mathbf{v}^\top \quad (12)$$

Calling the first term W and its rows \mathbf{w}_i^\top , we arrive at the following:

$$R^* R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_1^\top + ||\mathbf{t}_2|| \mathbf{v}^\top \\ \mathbf{w}_2^\top \\ \mathbf{w}_3^\top \end{bmatrix} / ||\mathbf{w}_3|| \quad (13)$$

in which the last two rows of the right hand side are independent from the value of \mathbf{v} . Since the rows of the right hand side form a orthonormal basis, we can recover the first one taking the cross product of the other two. Vector \mathbf{v} is therefore equal to:

$$\mathbf{v} = (\mathbf{w}_2 \times \mathbf{w}_3 / ||\mathbf{w}_3|| - \mathbf{w}_1) / ||\mathbf{t}_2|| \quad (14)$$

With the described procedure, we can enumerate through all possible matrices of intrinsics of two cameras K_1 and K_2 checking for the best upgrading homography, which can finally be refined through non-linear optimization.

In order to sample the space of calibration parameters we can safely assume, as customary, null skew and unit aspect ratio: this leaves the focal length and the principal point location as free parameters. However, as expected, the value of the plane at infinity is in general far more sensitive to errors in the estimation of focal length values rather than the image center. Thus, we can iterate just over focal lengths f_1 and f_2 assuming the principal point to be centered on the image; the error introduced with this approximation is normally well-within the radius of convergence of the subsequent non-linear optimization. The search space is therefore reduced to a bounded region of \mathbb{R}^2 .

To score each sampled point (f_1, f_2) , we consider the aspect ratio, skew and principal point location of the resulting transformed camera matrices and aggregate their respective value into a single cost function:

$$\{f_1, f_2\} = \arg \min_{f_1, f_2} \sum_{\ell=2}^n C^2(K_\ell) \quad (15)$$

where K_ℓ is the intrinsic parameters matrix of the ℓ -th camera after the Euclidean upgrade determined by (f_1, f_2) , and

$$\mathcal{C}(K) = \overbrace{w_{sk}|k_{1,2}|}^{\text{skew}} + \overbrace{w_{ar}|k_{1,1} - k_{2,2}|}^{\text{aspect ratio}} + \overbrace{w_{uo}|k_{1,3}| + w_{vo}|k_{2,3}|}^{\text{principal point}} \quad (16)$$

where $k_{i,j}$ denotes the entry (i, j) of K and w are suitable weights, computed as in (Pollefeys et al., 2002). The first term of (16) takes into account the skew, which is expected to be 0, the second one penalizes cameras with aspect ratio different from 1 and the last two weigh down cameras where the principal point is away from the image centre.

6 ON-LINE IMAGE ORIENTATION

The reconstruction procedure described above works in batch, meaning that SAMANTHA needs to have access to all the images at the same time. An interesting problem that is directly linked to self-localization in a known environment (Garro and Fusiello, 2010) is that of orienting a *new* image of the scene previously reconstructed. In order to compute features correspondences between the new image and the set of 3D points all the information acquired, namely the cameras network and the set of SIFT descriptors related to each 3D point, is exploited. First the most similar images to the current one are retrieved, then a subset of 3D points visible in these images is identified, and finally 2D - 3D correspondences are established.

6.1 Offline data pre-processing.

In order to support efficient on-line retrieval of the images, a Bag-of-Words (BoW) indexing scheme is implemented off-line (as in (Sivic and Zisserman, 2003)).

The first step is the codebook construction, which consists in clustering the descriptors associated to the 3D points and identifying the clusters centres as *visual words*. Two examples of efficient and scalable clustering techniques are vocabulary tree (Nister and Stewenius, 2006), that uses hierarchical k-means to recursively subdivide the feature space, and random forests (Philbin et al., 2007).

The second step computes a compact representation or *signature* of each image as the histogram of occurrences of visual word in the image. As customary (Sivic and Zisserman, 2003), a *term frequency - inverse document frequency* (TF-IDF) weighting is applied to these signatures. This weighting scheme, typically employed in text retrieval, considers visual words frequencies both in a single image and in the entire database. Indeed some visual words can be less distinctive due to a high frequency of appearance in the entire image database, and these items must be down-weighted; on the other hand, visual words appearing only in few images have a high distinctive power and should be up-weight.

6.2 Online image orientation.

In the online phase, the system first exploits the BoW indexing to retrieve the images most similar to the current one. SIFT keypoints are extracted from this image then each feature is assigned to a visual word of the codebook (using a data structure that support efficient neighborhood query, like kd-trees) and its related BoW signature is computed. Then the similarity between query and database images is computed using the cosine measure. A subset \tilde{D} of m most similar images is therefore determined.

The second step consists in selecting the SIFT features associated to the points of the 3D model visible from the images in \tilde{D} .

As a further additional constraint, only the features attached to 3D points that are visible from more than one view are selected. Then, a closest neighbour matching is performed between the features extracted from the new image and the features just selected, obtaining a set of correspondences between 2D image points and 3D model points. The exterior orientation of the camera can now be computed by a linear algorithm, either (Fiore, 2001) if the intrinsic parameter are known, or resection (Hartley and Zisserman, 2003) in the case of uncalibrated camera. MSAC is used to cope with outliers. A further non-linear refinement of camera orientation can be done by minimizing the reprojection error of the set of 3D points inliers.

We tested the performance of the online camera orientation on the ‘‘Piazza Br’’ set with a leave-one-out experiment. Each registered camera has been first removed from the dataset together with the related feature descriptors and then the localization algorithm has been run on the updated dataset. The original orientation of the camera computed by SAMANTHA is taken as ground truth.

In Tab. 1 the accuracy of our orientation algorithm is shown in terms of Euclidean distance of the camera centre with respect to the ground truth data and the residual rotation angle.

Method	Camera Centre Distance [m]	Residual Rotation Angle [deg]
Fiore	0.2509	0.56
Resection	3.0101	4.03
Fiore + refin	0.1270	0.29
Resection + refin	3.0022	4.00

Table 1: Camera orientation average error

7 RESULTS

We run SAMANTHA on the datasets provided by the workshop’s organizers. On the ‘‘Campidoglio’’, ‘‘Piazza Navona’’ and ‘‘Park Guell’’ sets the results were clearly incorrect, maybe because of a misunderstanding of the calibration model. On the other nine datasets SAMANTHA produced good results. ‘‘Piazza Erbe’’ and ‘‘Piazza Dante’’ were processed at half resolution because this results were already available and we did not have enough time to run new experiments. ‘‘St Jean Fountain’’ were processed at half resolution in order to reduce the computational load. All sets but ‘‘St Jean Fountain’’ were calibrated, so radial distortion had been removed beforehand and internal parameters were given as input. ‘‘St Jean Fountain’’, instead, did not have calibration parameters available: it has been processed by SAMANTHA using its auto-calibration feature, without taking the available EXIF data into account. Table 2 summarizes the results:

Figures 4 - 9 illustrate the results.

Computation times are not available, because we run the experiments on different computers, and the code is a mixture of C++ and Matlab. However it has been already proved analytically and empirically (Farenzena et al., 2009, Gherardi et al., 2010) that SAMANTHA is more efficient than sequential approaches, boosting the computational efficiency by one order of magnitude.

8 CONCLUSIONS

We presented SAMANTHA, a Structure and Motion pipeline that improves on the state of the art thanks to a hierarchical scheme based on views clustering. Our proposal is more efficient than sequential approaches, and more general, because it is able to process uncalibrated pictures (with no ancillary information).

Figure 4: Two views of the reconstruction of "Piazza Dante"

Figure 5: Reconstruction of "Pozzoveggiani" (left) and "Myson" (right)

Figure 6: Two views of the reconstruction of "Piazza Erbe"

Figure 7: Two views of the reconstruction of "Piazza Bra"

Figure 8: Two views of the reconstruction of "St Jean Fountain"

Figure 9: Reconstruction of "Castle-K19", "Fountain-K6", and "Herz-Jesu-K7"

Image set	resolution	images: orig/oriented	notes
Pozzoveggiani	1024x768	50/54	
Piazza Dante	2288x1712	39/39	half res
Piazza Erbe	2288x1712	183/259	half res
Piazza Bra	3008x2000	217/331	
Castle-K19	3072x2048	19/19	
Fountain-K6	3072x2048	6/6	
Herz-Jesu-K7	3072x2048	7/7	
Myson	3872x2592	18/18	
StJean Fount.n	6048x4032	66/66	half res autocalibrated
Piazza Navona	4000x3000	53/92	wrong
Campidoglio	3000x4000	34/56	wrong
Parc Guell	3000x4000	38/53	wrong

Table 2: Summary of results.

Future work will be aimed at bridging the “semantic web”, moving from an unstructured cloud of points to a higher level model that can be imported in any digital content creation software. Our first step in this direction is described in (Toldo and Fusiello, 2010).

Data and additional material are available from <http://profs.sci.univr.it/~fusiello/demo/samantha/>.

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